

Review of Turmeric as a medicinal herb

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Abstract- Turmeric is an ancient spice derived from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, which is a member of the ginger family (Zingiberaceae). Also known as ‘Golden Spice of India’ turmeric has been used in India for medicinal purposes for centuries. It has been used in traditional medicine as a household remedy for various diseases, including biliary disorders, anorexia, cough, diabetic wounds, hepatic disorders, rheumatism and sinusitis. In addition to its use as a spice and pigment, turmeric and its constituents mainly curcumin and essential oils shows a wide spectrum of biological actions. These include its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti-mutagenic, anticoagulant, antifertility, anti-diabetic, antibacterial, antifungal, antiprotozoal, antiviral, anti-fibrotic, anti-venom, antiulcer, hypotensive and hypercholesteremic activities. Modern interest on turmeric started in 1970's when researchers found that the herb may possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Safety evaluation studies indicate that both turmeric and curcumin are well tolerated at a very high dose without any toxic effects. Thus, turmeric and its constituents have the potential for the development of modern medicine for the treatment of various diseases

Index Terms: Turmeric, *Curcuma longa*, sprain Haridra’ or ‘Haldi, Curcumin.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Turmeric has also been used for centuries in Ayurvedic medicine, which integrates the medicinal properties of herbs with food. This extraordinary herb has found its way into the spotlight in the west and rest of globe, because of its wide range of medicinal benefits. Use of turmeric dates back nearly 4000 years to the Vedic culture in India. It is extensively used in Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha medicine as home remedy for various diseases 1,2. Turmeric, derived from the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, (family Zingiberaceae) is a perennial plant having short stem with large oblong leaves, and bears ovate, pyriform or oblong rhizomes, which are often branched and brownish-yellow in colour. Turmeric a native of South-East Asia, is used as a food additive (spice), preservative and colouring agent in Asian countries including China, Bangladesh and South East Asia. It is primarily cultivated in China, Taiwan, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Burma (Myanmar), Nigeria, Australia, West Indies, Peru, Jamaica and some other Caribbean and Latin American countries. Accounting for about 78 percent of world turmeric production, India is the largest producer of turmeric 3. It is also the biggest consumer and exporter of turmeric. Turmeric is considered as auspicious and is a part of religious rituals. In old Hindu medicine, it is extensively used for the treatment of sprain and swelling caused by injury. In recent times, traditional India medicine uses turmeric powder for the treatment of biliary disorders, anorexia, coryza, cough, diabetes, wounds, hepatic disorders, rheumatism and sinusitis etc.

Plant Description:

A relative of ginger, turmeric is a perennial plant that grows 5 - 6 feet high in the tropical produce rhizomes, which then produce stems and roots for new plants. Turmeric is fragrant and has a bitter, somewhat sharp taste. Although it grows in many tropical locations, the majority of turmeric is grown in India, where it is used as a main ingredient in curry.

Parts Used:

The roots, or rhizomes and bulbs, are used in medicinal and food preparations. They are generally boiled and then dried, turning into the familiar yellow powder. Curcumin, the active ingredient, has antioxidant properties, which some claim may be as strong as vitamins C and E. Other substances in this herb have antioxidant properties as well.

Available Forms:

Turmeric is available in the following forms:

- Capsules containing powder
- Fluid extract

· Tincture

Because bromelain increases the absorption and anti-inflammatory effects of curcumin, it is often combined with turmeric products.

Health benefits of turmeric in our daily life

1. It is a natural antiseptic and antibacterial agent, useful in disinfecting cuts and burns.
2. When combined with cauliflower, it has shown to prevent prostate cancer and stop the growth of existing prostate cancer.
3. Prevented breast cancer from spreading to the lungs in mice.
4. May prevent melanoma and cause existing melanoma cells to commit suicide.
5. Reduces the risk of childhood leukaemia.
6. Is a natural liver detoxifier.
7. May prevent and slow the progression of Alzheimer's disease by removing amyloid plaque buildup in the brain.
8. May prevent metastases from occurring in many different forms of cancer.
9. It is a potent natural anti-inflammatory that works as well as many anti-inflammatory drugs but without the side effects.
10. Has shown promise in slowing the progression of multiple sclerosis in mice.
11. Is a natural painkiller and cox-2 inhibitor.
12. May aid in fat metabolism and help in weight management.
13. Has long been used in Chinese medicine as a treatment for depression.
14. Because of its anti-inflammatory properties, it is a natural treatment for arthritis and rheumatoid arthritis.
15. Boosts the effects of chemo drug paclitaxel and reduces its side effects.
16. Promising studies are underway on the effects of turmeric on pancreatic cancer.
17. Studies are ongoing in the positive effects of turmeric on multiple myeloma.
18. Has been shown to stop the growth of new blood vessels in tumors.
19. Speeds up wound healing and assists in remodelling of damaged skin.
20. May help in the treatment of psoriasis and other inflammatory skin conditions.

BOTANICAL INFORMATION OF TURMERIC

- Scientific name – *Curcuma Longa*
- Common name - Turmeric
- Family- Zingiberaceae
- Origin place- South East Asia
- Economic part – Dried rhizome
- Essential oil content – 2.5-7.2%
- *Curcuma longa* is an herbaceous perennial herb
- Curcumin (4 -7%) is the principle colouring pigment in turmeric

Geographical information

- The plant is native to Southern Asia and is cultivated extensively in temperate regions.
- It is grown on a larger scale in India, China, East India, Pakistan, Malaysia.
- India is a leading producer and exporter of turmeric in the world

- Andhra Pradesh alone occupies 35.0% of area and 47.0% of production
- It is grown in diverse tropical condition from sea level to 1500mm or more, under rainfall or irrigated condition
- It is grown on different types of soils it thrives best in well drained sandy or clay loam soil with a pH range of 4.5-7.5 with good organic status
- The number of cultivators are available in country and are known mostly by the name of locality where they are cultivated

- There are various species of Turmeric specifically belonging to different areas within the India and they are as follows

Name of Turmeric species	Approx. percentage	Curcumin	State
Lakadong	7-12%		Meghalaya
Alleppey	5%		Kerala
Madras	3%		Tamil Nadu
Rajapore	n/a		Maharashtra
Sangli	2-4%		Maharashtra
Erode	2-4%		Tamil Nadu
Nizamabad bulb	n/a		Telangana

Chemical Composition of Turmeric:

Also known as 'Haridra' or 'Haldi', turmeric contains protein (6.3%), fat (5.1%), minerals (3.5%), carbohydrates (69.4%) and moisture (23.1%). The essential oil (5-8%) obtained by steam distillation of rhizomes has α -phellandrene (1%), sabinene (0.6%), cineol (1%), borneol (0.5%), zingiberene (25%) and sesquiterpenes (53%) 5. Curcumin is the principal curcuminoid of turmeric. The other two are desmethoxycurcumin and bis-desmethoxycurcumin. Curcumin gives yellow colour to turmeric and is now recognized as being responsible for most of the therapeutic effects. It is estimated that 2-5% of turmeric is curcumin. Curcumin was first isolated from turmeric in 1815 and the structure was delineated in 1910 as diferuloylmethane 6. Most currently available preparation of curcumin contains approximately 77% diferuloylmethane, 18% desmethoxycurcumin and 5% bis-dimethoxy curcumin. Curcumin is hydrophobic in nature and frequently soluble in dimethylsulfoxide, acetone, ethanol and oils. It has absorption maxima around 425nm. When exposed to acidic conditions, the colour of turmeric/curcumin turns from yellow to deep red, and the form in which it is used in various religious ceremonies 7.

A World of Turmeric: Turmeric, a golden spice, had been used by the people of the Indian subcontinent for centuries with no known side effects, not only as a component of food but also to treat a wide variety of ailments. As far as documented evidence, it is used daily in India for at least 6000 years as a medicine, beauty aid, cooking spice, a dye and a lot more. Turmeric was mentioned in the writings of Marco Polo concerning his 1280 journey to China and India and it was first introduced to Europe in the 13th century by Arab traders. Vasco de Gama, a Portuguese sailor during 15th century, after his visit to India, truly introduced spices to the West 8. For at least 1000 years Chinese Medicine has used Turmeric especially for the Spleen, Stomach, and Liver Meridians. They use it to stimulate and strengthen the blood, to purify, to decrease blood pressure, to reduce abdominal pain, anti-biotic, anti-viral and an analgesic. Because of its colour and taste, turmeric was named "Indian saffron" in Europe.

Today, India is the primary exporter of turmeric (known as “haldi” in India). Although its ability to preserve food through its antioxidant mechanism, to give colour to food and to add taste to the food is well known, its health promoting effects are less well recognized or appreciated. It was once considered a cure for jaundice, an appetite suppressant and a digestive 9. In Indian and Chinese medicines, turmeric was used as anti-inflammatory agents to treat gas, colic, toothaches, chest pains, and menstrual difficulties. This spice was also used to help with stomach and liver problems, to heal wounds and lighten scars and as a cosmetic.

Pharmacological information of Turmeric

Healing Properties Overview:

Besides flavouring food, turmeric, affectionately called as “*Kitchen Queen*”, has been used in traditional medicine as a household remedy for various diseases, including biliary disorders, anorexia, cough, diabetic wounds, hepatic disorders, rheumatism and sinusitis etc. Turmeric has been shown to have a wide spectrum of biological actions. These include its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-carcinogenic, anti- mutagenic, anticoagulant, anti-fertility, anti- diabetic, antibacterial, antifungal, anti- protozoal, antiviral, anti-fibrotic, antivenin, antiulcer, hypotensive and hypercholesteremic activities.

Its anticancer effect is mainly mediated through induction of apoptosis. Its anti-inflammatory, anticancer and antioxidant roles may be clinically exploited to control rheumatism, carcinogenesis and oxidative stress-related pathogenesis. Therapeutic uses include: AIDS/HIV, anaemia, cancer, diabetes, digestion, food poisoning, gall stones etc. It reduces fevers, diarrhea, urinary disorders, insanity, poisoning, cough and lactation problems in general. Clinically, turmeric has already been used to reduce post-operative inflammation. Safety evaluation studies indicate that both turmeric and curcumin are well tolerated at a very high dose without any toxic effects. Thus, turmeric has the potential for the development of modern medicine for the treatment of various diseases.

Turmeric as First Aid:

Researches has shown turmeric as homeostatic, able to stop the bleeding of wound and a vulnerary, a great healer of wounds due to being both anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial. Turmeric powder has healing effect on both aseptic and septic wounds in rats and rabbits.

The Skin’s Beautician:

Turmeric is a skin’s food: it purifies and nourishes the blood and results in healthy and glowing skin. Due to its anti-bacterial and anti- septic properties it is excellent for skin diseases like eczema, acne, skin cancers etc. and helps in preventing premature ageing. Turmeric is used in the formulation of cosmetics and sunscreens.

Pain and Inflammation:

Inflammation is generally regarded as a source of many health challenges. Turmeric is an excellent anti-inflammatory herb; easing conditions such as bursitis, arthritis, back pain etc and plays an important role in inflammation. The anti-inflammatory action of turmeric includes lowering histamine levels and increasing the production of natural cortisone by adrenal glands. It inhibits release of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α and the gene that makes inflammatory COX-2 enzymes. Perhaps Turmeric’s most important anti-inflammatory mechanism is its effects on the Prostaglandins (PGs), a large family of potent lipids produced by the body. PG1 and PG3 calm the body while PG2 inflames the body. Turmeric is a potent inhibitor of cyclooxygenase 5- lipoxygenase and also 5-HETE production in neutrophils. Reducing these enzymes means less arachidonic acid metabolism, which means less PG2, which means less pain and inflammation. In patients, undergoing surgery, oral application of turmeric reduces post-operative inflammation.

Blood, Liver, Heart and Respiratory System:

Turmeric is a potent blood purifier and helps to create new blood. Turmeric also protects liver from toxins and pathogens. It is known to destroy major hepatotoxins, like aflatoxin and to rebuild the liver. Turmeric increases the secretion of bile promotes bilification and may prevent cholelithiasis. Turmeric also removes cholesterol from the liver and inhibits its assimilation. Turmeric’s protective effect on the heart (cardiovascular system) include lowering cholesterol and triglyceride levels decreasing susceptibility of low density lipoproteins (LDL) to lipid peroxidation and inhibiting platelet aggregation. Turmeric protects against heart diseases by lowering high blood cholesterol level and by preventing blood clotting which can lead to heart attack and stroke. Inhibition of platelets aggregation by C. longa constituents is thought to be via potentiation of prostacyclin synthesis and inhibition of thrombin synthesis. The Awesome Anti-Oxidant: The antioxidant activity of turmeric was reported as early as 1975. It acts as a scavenger of oxygen free radicals. It can protect hemoglobin from oxidation. Water and fat-soluble extracts of turmeric and

curcumin, its main active constituent, exhibits strong antioxidant activity, comparable to vitamins C, E and Beta-Carotene. Oxidation by free radicals is linked with accelerated aging and virtually every major chronic disease including atherosclerosis, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, cataracts, and rheumatoid arthritis. In vitro, curcumin can significantly inhibit the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) like superoxide anions, H₂O₂ and nitrite radical generation by activated macrophages. An in vitro study measuring the effect of curcumin on endothelial heme oxygenase-1, an inducible stress protein, was conducted utilizing bovine aortic endothelial cells. Incubation (18 hours) with curcumin resulted in enhanced cellular resistance to oxidative damage. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) also play an important role in cell mediated cytotoxicity (CMC) of the immune system. Numerous reports indicate that turmeric could mediate both pro-oxidant and antioxidant roles, making turmeric usage a consumer choice for feeling and looking young; preventing premature ageing; cancer and tumors prevention, liver protection, removing oxidized cholesterol thereby preventing heart attacks; reducing pain and acute (injuries) and chronic inflammations (arthritis).

Turmeric for Stomach and Intestine: And pathogens Constituents of *Curcuma longa* exert several protective effects on the Gastro-Intestinal (GI) system. Sodium curcumin ate inhibited intestinal spasm and p- tolymethylcarbinol, a turmeric component, increased gastrin, secretin, bicarbonate, and pancreatic enzyme secretion. Turmeric has also been shown to inhibit ulcer formation caused by stress, alcohol, indomethacin, pyloric ligation, and reserpine, significantly increasing gastric wall mucus in rats subjected to these gastrointestinal insults. Research has also confirmed the digestive benefits of turmeric. Turmeric acts as a cholagogue, stimulating bile production, thus, increasing the bodies' ability to digest fats, improving digestion and eliminating toxins from the liver. Turmeric powder has beneficial effect on the stomach. It increases mucin secretion in rabbits and may thus act as gastro-protectant against irritants. Curcumin has some good effects on the intestine also. Antispasmodic activity of sodium curcumin ate was observed in isolated guinea pig ileum. Curcumin also enhances intestinal lipase, sucrase and maltase activity. Turmeric is traditionally used for weak stomachs, poor digestion, dyspepsia, to normalize metabolism, to help digest protein, and to increase the bio-availability of food and the ability of the stomach to withstand digestive acids. Turmeric reduces the intensity of cysteamine-induced duodenal ulcers, increases the gastric wall mucus, and also normalizes gastric juices.

Ears, Eyes, Nose and Mouth:

Due to its astringent, anti-biotic and anti-inflammatory properties, turmeric is excellent for the toothaches or tooth decay and is used in preparations of toothpastes. It tones the gums and destroys bacteria whose acidic wastes cause cavities. One of the main causes of eye disease, especially cataracts, is the oxidation of lens in your eyes. Turmeric taken internally decreases the oxidation of the lens by causing a significant induction of glutathione-S-transferase isozyme rGST8-8 in the lens epithelium. Turmeric also works efficiently for stopping nosebleeds, helps to clear the sinuses, restore a more acute sense of smell, and helps to purify the mind and brain. Data are also available showing that turmeric powder is used in Indian and Chinese medicines for treating cough, sputum, sinusitis, dyspnoea, toothaches, ear and eye pains etc.

Antifertility activity and Female Reproductive System:

Petroleum ether and aqueous extracts of turmeric rhizomes show 100% antifertility effect in rats when fed orally. Implantation is completely inhibited by these extracts. Curcumin inhibits 5 α -reductase, which converts testosterone to 5 dihydrotestosterone, thereby inhibiting the growth of flank organs in hamster.

Curcumin also inhibits human sperm motility and has the potential for the development of a novel intravaginal contraceptive. Turmeric regulates menses, decreases intensity and pain of periods, decreases amenorrhoea and decreases uterine tumors. Turmeric is a mild and supportive uterine stimulant.

Antimicrobial activity of Turmeric:

Turmeric extract and the essential oil of *Curcuma longa* inhibit the growth of a variety of bacteria, parasites, and pathogenic fungi. The aqueous extract of turmeric rhizomes has antibacterial effects. Most importantly, curcumin also shows anti-HIV (human immunodeficiency virus) activity by inhibiting the HIV-1 integrase needed for viral replication 46. It also inhibits UV light induced HIV gene expression. Thus curcumin and its analogues may have the potential for novel drug development against HIV.

Turmeric for Nervous disorders, Detox and Immunity:

Curcumin, active constituent of turmeric, can bind with heavy metals such as cadmium and lead, thereby reducing the toxicity of these heavy metals. This property of curcumin explains its protective action to the brain. Curcumin acts as an inhibitor for cyclooxygenase, 5-lipoxygenase and glutathione S-transferase. Curcumin and manganese complex of curcumin offer protective action against vascular dementia by exerting antioxidant activity. Turmeric is one of the 10

best herbs used to treat poisoning and to purify blood. It detoxifies the body and mind, helping the body to cure itself. One sure sign of this is that it increases the level of the enzyme glutathione S-transferase (GST), which is essential to detoxification. In addition it helps beautify the skin and improve the complexion, promoting circulation and nutrition to the surface of the body. It vitalizes the body's own natural healing energy through its action of strengthening digestion and circulation, and aiding in the regulation of all bodily systems. Turmeric with its potent anti-microbial and anti-oxidant activities interferes with the ability of microbes and viruses to replicate them and it increases body's Immune system's ability to fight the infection and ultimately helps in enhancing the immunity of body. Curcumin can also help the body fight off cancer should some cells escape apoptosis. When researchers looked at the lining of the intestine after ingestion of curcumin, they found that CD4+ T-helper and B type immune cells were greater in number. In addition to this localized immune stimulation, curcumin also enhances immunity in general. Researchers in India have documented increased antibodies and more immune action in mice given regular turmeric dosages.

Turmeric for Diabetes:

Turmeric is an important herb in most Ayurvedic treatments of diabetes as it lowers blood sugar, increases glucose metabolism and potentate's insulin activity more than three-fold. Part of the action might be due to its chromium content. Curcumin prevents galactose-induced cataract formation at very low doses. Both turmeric and curcumin decrease blood sugar level in alloxan-induced diabetes in rat. Curcumin also decreases advanced glycation end products induced complications in diabetes mellitus.

Therapeutic Properties:

Turmeric contains curcumin and curcuminoids it is a first rate natural remedy for arthritis, it has an anti-inflammatory ingredient that can help alleviate pain. It can also help protect the gallbladder and liver and provide a defence against cancer. Curcumin can also help inhibit the formation of cancer in breast tissue. Experiment on animal shows that curcumin slashed the risk of colon cancer by almost 60%, this phytochemical seems to neutralize cancer-causing compounds, stop cancerous changes in the cells and directly fight substances that enable carcinogens to spread and wreak havoc. Turmeric also triggers better bile flow, which helps digest fats and reduces the risk of gallstones. It also helps generate the secretion of several enzymes that assist the liver in breaking down and metabolizing certain toxic substances. Some of these same phytochemicals inhibit the oxidative damage that allows cholesterol to coagulate and cling to the inside of arteries. Turmeric /curcumin is about half as effective as corticosteroids, but it doesn't have bad side effect as corticosteroids, this drug is use for the treatment of arthritis, but they can cause fluid retention and bloating, elevate blood pressure, encourage intestinal bleeding, ulcer formation and increase the risk of osteoporosis.

Uses and Utilization

- Turmeric contains curcumin, a substance with powerful anti-inflammatory and antioxidant property. It contains an bioactive compound with medicinal properties.
- It is used in treatment of various diseases like heart diseases, cancer, metabolic syndrome, Alzheimer's disease and various degenerative conditions.
- Turmeric can increase the antioxidant capacity of the body by neutralizing free radicals present in our body.
- Curcumin can boost brain derived neurotropic factor (BDNF) This is a gene that is involve in making a protein responsible for promoting the life of neurons and helps to fight against various degenerative processes of our brain.
- Turmeric is an essential component which is used in treatment of cancer. Curcumin leads to several changes on the molecular level that may help to prevent and perhaps even treat cancer.
- Arthritis patient respond well when curcumin supplements are provided.
- Turmeric has many benefits against depression also.
- Curcumin may help delay aging and age-related chronic diseases.

Cosmetics

1. The juice of raw turmeric is applied to the skin as a paste, kept for around thirty minutes and then washed off. It adds glow to the skin.
2. It is an essential ingredient of the traditional bathing ritual of Indian marriages where it is applied along with sandal wood paste before the bath.
3. It is believed that regular bathing in water containing turmeric reduces growth of body hair.
4. Regular turmeric use is said to make the skin fair, soft and smooth.
5. Turmeric is used for spots caused due to pigmentation or blotches and also for diseases like eczema.

Potential Uses of Turmeric

There are many other uses of turmeric. Turmeric:

1. Improves the ability of the liver to remove toxic chemicals taken into the body.
2. Stops the oxidation of the body's cholesterol which is the leading cause of diabetic heart disease and atherosclerosis
3. Provides a natural source of vitamin B6 which keeps homocysteine levels low protecting the walls of the blood vessels
4. Lowers cholesterol
5. Provides protection from neurodegenerative diseases including Alzheimer's
6. Aids in the treatment of cystic fibrosis
7. Treats digestive Disorders
8. Reduces inflammation of the middle layer of the eye
9. Treats liver disease including cirrhosis, hepatitis, jaundice and enlarged hepatic ducts
10. Relieves the pain of osteoarthritis
11. Relieves menstrual cramp pain
12. Heals bacterial infections
13. Improves skin conditions and diseases including psoriasis
14. Defends or potentially defends against HIV

Conclusion

It is a wonder that a natural yellow pigment, turmeric, which has been consumed in India since the second millennium BC in both medicine and food has become one of the most cited natural molecule in terms of its capacity to deliver a multitude of health guarding effects as studied and established by modern scientific community around the globe. For the last few decades, extensive work has been done to establish the biological activities and pharmacological actions of turmeric and its extracts. It has been used in ayurvedic medicine since ancient times, with various biological applications. Various studies are in progress for using turmeric in drug-development. Although the crude extract has numerous medicinal applications, clinical applications can be made only after extensive research on its bioactivity, mechanism of action, pharmaco-therapeutics and toxicity studies. However, as turmeric and its compounds show a wide spectrum of biological activities, it would be easier to develop new drugs from turmeric after extensive studies on its mechanism of action and pharmacological effects. Recent years have seen an increased enthusiasm in treating various diseases with natural products. Turmeric/Curcumin is a non-toxic, highly promising natural antioxidant, spice having a wide spectrum of biological functions. It is expected that turmeric and its constituents specially curcumin and essential oils may find application as a novel drug in the near future to control various diseases, including inflammatory disorders, carcinogenesis, HIV/AIDS, diabetes, oxidative stress-induced pathogenesis and a lot more. All of these studies should further add to the usefulness of turmeric and its constituents specially curcumin and essential oil. Overall, due to its usage, biological safety, combined with its cost and efficacy, and thousands of years of experimentation justify calling turmeric

“The Golden Spice of Life”.

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